

Equilibrium Studies on the System 4,6-Dimethyl-2-mercaptopyrimidine–Bivalent Metal Ion Complexes

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In continuation of our earlier studies¹ on the coordinating tendencies of the substituted pyrimidines, we now report the formation constants of binary complexes of bivalent metal ions Co, Ni and Zn with 4,6-dimethyl-2-mercaptopyrimidine and ternary complexes of 4,6-dimethyl-2-mercaptopyrimidine with bivalent Co, Ni and Zn in presence of other ligands, such as oxalic acid, malonic acid, bipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline and ethylenediamine at 35° and ionic strength of 0.1 M (KNO₃) in aqueous medium.

Results and Discussion

Binary systems: The potentiometric titration curves of monoprotonated 2-mercaptopyrimidine (MP) and 4,6-dimethyl-2-mercaptopyrimidine (DMMP) indicate a steep inflection at $\alpha = 1$ followed by buffer region at higher pH. The first dissociation of both ligands probably involves the removal of a proton from N₃H of the pyrimidine ring^{2,3}. The second is obviously due to the dissociation of proton from C₂-SH group of the pyrimidine.

The dimethyl substitution at 4 and 6 positions on the pyrimidine ring of DMMP makes it more basic than the 2-mercaptopyrimidine (MP) due to its electron-donating character. Similarly, the stability constants ($\log K_{ML}^M$) of the ligand 4,6-dimethyl-2-mercaptopyrimidine is found to be more than the metal complexes of 2-mercaptopyrimidine (Table 1). This observed trend is in tune with their basicity order.

Ternary systems: The ternary stability constants pertaining to the interaction of substituted pyrimidine and bivalent metal ion with other ligands are compiled in Table 2.

Usually, the role of secondary ligands on the sta-

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF
2-MERCAPTOPYRIMIDINE AND 4,6-DIMETHYL-
2-MERCAPTOPYRIMIDINE WITH BIVALENT METAL IONS

$I = 0.1 M$ (KNO₃) aqueous medium, Temp. = 35°

	2-Mercapto- pyrimidine	4,6-Dimethyl- 2-mercaptopyrimidine
pK_1	2.03	3.65
pK_2	7.01	8.63
Ni ^{II}	4.14	5.14
Co ^{II}	3.21	4.46
Zn ^{II}	3.52	4.35

^aStandard deviations are within ± 0.04 log units

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES
($\log K_{MAL}^M$) OF 4,6-DIMETHYL-2-MERCAPTOPYRIMIDINE IN
PRESENCE OF OTHER LIGANDS AND BIVALENT METAL IONS

$I = 0.1 M$ (KNO₃) aqueous medium, Temp. = 35°

	Co ^{II}	$\Delta \log K$	Ni ^{II}	$\Delta \log K$	Zn ^{II}	$\Delta \log K$
Ox	7.30	-0.90	8.69	-0.47	7.84	-0.30
Mal	7.17	-0.25	7.87	-0.50	7.71	-0.71
Bipy	9.22	-0.22	11.15	-0.76	8.84	-0.65
Phen	9.48	-0.91	12.04	-0.77	10.63	-0.93
En	7.30	-2.84	10.11	-1.84	8.55	-1.06

bility of 1 : 1 metal-ligand complex is quantified in terms of $\Delta \log K$. The parameter $\Delta \log K$ is the difference between overall 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes and the corresponding 1 : 1 binary complexes. Thus, if $\Delta \log K$ values are positive or less negative then the ternary complexes are more stable than the binary complex, and if they are negative, the binary complexes are more stable. However, it should be noted that negative values of $\Delta \log K$ do not preclude the formation of ternary complexes in solution.

The perusal of the $\Delta \log K$ values shows that the

binary (1 : 1) complexes are more stable than the ternary (1 : 1 : 1) complexes because in all the systems negative $\Delta \log K$ values have been obtained. However, it can be seen that the system *m*-Ox/Mal-L has less negative $\Delta \log K$ values than the other system [M-Phen/Bipy-L]. This trend can be explained in terms of π -interactions. Doraswamy and Bhattacharya⁴ showed that Cu^{II}-Bipy/Phen (1 : 1) complex has discriminating qualities towards secondary ligands to be bonded. It prefers O-O > N-O > N-N and this sequence is supported by the argument that M(II) $\rightarrow$ Bipy/Phen π -interaction makes ternary complexes more stable (less negative or positive $\Delta \log K$ values). In the present case, the substituted pyrimidine due to its aromatic character and N and S as donor atoms also behave as π -acceptor. Hence, with this ligand the stability order with respect to secondary ligands is found to be : Ox > Mal > Bipy > Phen > en. The order with respect to metals is in conformity with Irving-Williams order.

Experimental

The experimental method consisted of the potentiometric titration of each ligand with standard NaOH solution in the absence and presence of the metal ions. The ionic strength of the solution was maintained constant in the course of the titration by the use of a medium containing 0.10 M KNO₃ and relatively low concentration of ligand and metal ion. Pre-saturated nitrogen was passed through the solution during titration and the temperature was maintained at 35°.

A Beckman G pH meter with glass and calomel electrode assembly was used to determine the hydrogen ion concentration. The electrode system was calibrated by direct titration with acetic acid and the pH meter reading was compared with the actual hydro-

gen ion concentration as calculated from the literature data⁵. The pH regions below 3.5 and above 10.5 were calibrated by direct measurement of the hydrogen ion concentration in HCl and NaOH respectively. The equilibrium constants correspond to the reference state of infinitely dilute reacting species in a medium of 0.10 M KNO₃. The pH meter readings were plotted against α (moles of base added per mole of ligand) or *m* (moles of base added per mole of metal ion). The acid dissociation constants of the ligands were calculated from the potentiometric data using the computer program PKAS⁶. All the binary and ternary stability constants were computed using the computer program BEST⁷.

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